

CREATION OF LEGAL BASIS FOR DEEPENING REFORMS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: In this article, the creation of the legal basis for deepening reforms in the preschool education system and its condition is discussed.

Keywords: modernization, upbringing, education, theory, On-line, modern education, methods, scientific research, level of knowledge, preschool education, pedagogical staff, legal basis.

Enter. Preschool education - education system is considered the foundation, because the potential of those who determine the country's development in the future depends on the effective functioning of this system. For this reason, the leadership of Uzbekistan focuses on the development of this industry, on world standards appropriate educational system and its modern attaches great importance to the establishment of management.

Taking into account the above, the modernization and reform of the method of managing the preschool education process is gaining special relevance. It is one of the most important tasks to bring the innovations created in the preschool education system into the daily pedagogical process of educational institutions.

Analysis and results. Bringing innovative activities to preschool educational institutions and testing them creates a foundation for rapid development of children's cognitive activities at all stages of education, and fundamental reform of the educational system. Bringing innovative approaches to the activity of a preschool educational institution allows to ensure the improvement of the quality and efficiency of the educational process in the future. Preschool education system is the primary, most basic link of continuous education. According to the scientific conclusions of experts, 70 percent of all the information and information that a person receives during his life is received by the age of 5 years. This fact alone clearly shows how important the education received in the preschool educational institution is for our children to grow up as mature and well-rounded individuals.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, noted, "No matter what field we choose, we cannot achieve any changes or a prosperous life without educating modern mature personnel. Such the personnel of the nation so glom gene pool preparation, first of all, before school education from the system begins »¹

¹The speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the meeting dedicated to the improvement of the preschool education system. Young people press club. - "Marifat" newspaper. 1 of 2017 november - No. 87 (9048).

One of the most necessary conditions for achieving the main goal envisaged by these works is related to the provision of high professional training of pedagogues and the modernization of activities of pre-school educational institutions.

Currently, serious work is being done to improve this system, in particular, its content. As a logical continuation of these works, it is aimed to study, scientifically analyze, generalize the existing advanced experiences and work methods in the field of adapting the content of preschool education to modern requirements, and convey it to the leaders and pedagogues of this field.

In the period of new development of Uzbekistan, the legal framework aimed at the development of the industry in the country is of great importance in the implementation of these goals. The work in this direction began immediately after the first presidential elections in New Uzbekistan in December 2016.

Further improvement of the pre-school education system, strengthening the material and technical base, expanding the network of pre-school educational institutions, providing qualified pedagogical personnel, radically improving the level of preparation of children for school education, implementing modern educational programs and technologies in the educational process, In order to create conditions for all-round intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2016 "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021" No. PQ-2707 was adopted. Among the main objectives and directions of the "Program for the further improvement of the preschool education system for 2017-2021" approved by this decision is the creation of conditions for comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children, taking into account advanced foreign experience.

Also, the decision PQ-3261 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of preschool education" indicates the existing systemic shortcomings and the reasons that prevent the full implementation of the state policy in the field of preschool education, in particular:

firstly, the current state of pre-school education management does not allow timely identification and elimination of systemic problems, development and introduction of modern innovative technologies in this field, including the non-state sector;

secondly, public-private partnership mechanisms aimed at attracting investments in the field of preschool education, including the establishment of social and universal preschool educational institutions, their material and technical re-equipment, and the use of advanced pedagogical technologies, have not been introduced;

thirdly, the current state of the infrastructure and material and technical base of preschool educational institutions does not allow to ensure full coverage of children in preschool educational institutions, the population of the country the increase in number leads to overcrowding of some pre-school educational institutions;

fourthly, the preparation of teaching-methodical, didactic (including games and toys) materials and fiction literature reflecting national cultural-historical values and arousing interest in reading from childhood and introducing them into the activities of preschool educational institutions do not meet modern requirements;

fifth, the current system of personnel training and retraining cannot provide the field of preschool education with highly qualified specialists who are able to solve the issues of raising and comprehensive development of children at a professional level;

sixthly, the low level of the financial incentive system for the employees of pre-school educational institutions does not allow to attract qualified personnel;

seventhly, shortcomings in the organization of the work of regional health authorities on providing medical services to children in preschool educational institutions lead to a decrease in the effectiveness of preventive measures to protect the life and health of children, including ensuring healthy nutrition.²

According to the decision, a commission was established for the critical study of the preschool education system and development of proposals for its further improvement, and among its main tasks, the following were defined:

- review of state requirements for the organization of quality preschool education, taking into account advanced foreign experience in the field of harmonious development of preschool children;

- after studying the existing practice and advanced foreign experience, introducing a simplified procedure for licensing the activities of non-state preschool educational institutions, preparing proposals for improving their organizational and legal forms .

Further expansion of state and non-state networks of preschool educational institutions, creation of conditions for the formation of a healthy competitive environment between state and non-state preschool educational institutions, introduction of new forms of preschool educational institutions under the conditions of state and private sector partnership, as well as the Republic of Uzbekistan

In order to ensure the effective organization of the activities of the Ministry of Preschool Education, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2017 "On the organization of the activities of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PQ-3305 was adopted. As noted in the commentary to this decision: "...today, the issue of fundamentally improving the activities of preschool educational institutions, increasing the coverage of preschool children, and creating a modern system in all respects, having studied advanced foreign experience, remains urgent."³

In this decision, in order to eliminate existing problems in the reform of the preschool education system, the decision envisages the implementation of wide-scale measures, including the effective organization of the process of improving the qualifications of pedagogues and managers, using modern pedagogical and information technologies, the advanced experience of foreign countries, educational institutions provision of highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge is established.

of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2017 , "On measures to fundamentally improve the management of the preschool education

²2017 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan On September 9, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve the preschool education system" Decision No. PQ-3261. // "People's word", September 11, 2017 issue

³Legal information national base (www.lex.uz), 2017 . "Khalk sozi " newspaper , October 3, 2017

system", "Preschool education is considered the primary link of the continuous education system, and it is excellent in raising a healthy and well-rounded child and preparing him for school." is important.

As a result, as we mentioned above, the level of coverage of 3-6 year old children in preschool educational institutions in the regions was 13.9% in 2016, and in 2017 this indicator increased to 22.5%. In the preschool education system, 2107 preschool educational institutions were reconstructed and built in 2017, 2195 kindergartens were overhauled.

of the President of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2017 "

On measures to fundamentally improve the management of the preschool education system", ensuring the intellectual, moral, taste and physical development of our children based on foreign experience, small age children with state and competitive kindergartens and kindergartens, introduction of modern forms, methods and technologies in educational processes, provision of institutions with toys, books and manuals, training of qualified educators and pedagogues, expansion of staff motivation opportunities, permanent maintenance of buildings and provision of heat , it was necessary to solve important issues such as providing children with quality food and providing medical assistance when necessary.

This education was based on important activities such as preparing children for school, improving their literacy, and improving their abilities

. The specialists analyzed the system's condition and the possibilities to improve its operation in a short period of time, and cooperation relations with advanced countries such as Japan and South Korea began.

These works were carried out in all regions. The activities of all pre-school educational institutions were re-examined, the composition of the children being educated in them and the teachers working in them were analyzed. As a result, schools start from the age of 6 The number of gifted children admitted to "0" classes has increased significantly.

As a result, in 2017, 214 state and private kindergartens in cities and districts were repaired capially and 152 were repaired. In 2018, 1,400 state and private preschools were opened in the republic, and enrollment of children in kindergartens increased to 33%.⁴

In 2016-2017, the increasing efficiency of the use of available places in preschool educational institutions means that the demand for preschool educational institutions is increasing.

In addition to these legal documents, a number of decrees and decisions were adopted. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 The relevant sections of the Decree No. PF-4947 "On the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" serve as a program for activities aimed at the development of the sector .

⁴Uzbekistan Republic of the State Statistics Committee No. 01/2-01-19-84 dated January 19, 2018 gave information based on prepared .

Summary. In the Strategy of Actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, directions ⁵such as "Further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the efficiency of training of highly qualified personnel" are defined, in this regard, introduction of modern mechanisms of preschool education management, modernization of activities of preschool educational institutions, continuous improvement of the professional knowledge of pedagogical staff of preschool educational institutions. it is important to achieve the quality and efficiency of qualified pedagogic staff by creating conditions favorable to renewal, retraining and improving their skills. In addition to the ongoing work, today there is a need to retrain and upgrade the educational environment of preschool educational institutions, to improve the use of the educational environment, and to modernize the activities of preschool educational institutions

⁵Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". - Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 6, Article 70.

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